

A new approach to mammal specimen storage at LACM

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The Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County (LACM) mammal collection has about 80,000 specimens housed in cabinets of various sizes in the primary collections space. Skins, skulls, and skeletons have traditionally been organized in a single mixed series for each species, with multiple preparations stored together in the same drawer. In 2019 we undertook a large cryofumigation and taxonomic reordering project, with a secondary goal of freeing up existing storage space for future acquisitions. We decided to approach specimen storage in a new way and reinstalled specimen skins and skeletons preparations separately. By doing so, we discovered this was an exceptionally efficient use of space and freed up 30 quarter cabinets, or about 15% of our total storage space. Approaching the storage of specimen parts by preparation type allowed us to optimize drawer spacing and specimen density, thus making it easier to integrate overflow specimens and accommodate future expansion. This process also improved collections management of skeletal material in many ways, including specimen security and stability. We can confidently track and find specimen parts because our reinstallation included a thorough inventory and the incorporation of location data in our database. To solve issues of finite space, curators and collections managers will need to consider new organizational approaches beyond the typical or “traditional” ways. Relational databases that tie together the location of parts within a specimen record provide opportunities and flexibility for novel storage organization of varying collections materials.

